

ISOLATION AND PURIFICATION OF NICOTINE FROM TOBACCO LEAVES USING EUTECTIC DEEP SOLVENT

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ABSTRACT

Tobacco smoke contains over 4,000 distinct chemicals that can be harmful to people in various ways. Because nicotine stimulates the production of serotonin, also known as the pleasure fluid, in the brain, it is the most addictive of these substances. In many countries, tobacco use is a leading cause of death and a major contributor to a number of chronic diseases. Because of this, there is a greater need to extract nicotine, the most addictive substance, and deliver it to the body in ways other than smoking and burning, such as eating, breathing, or skin contact. Therefore, the term “therapeutic use of nicotine as a smoking cessation aid” refers to the use of nicotine to help you quit smoking. Choline chloride/ethyl alcohol, a deep eutectic solvent, was used in this research to extract the highest purity nicotine (3-(1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinyl) pyridine) from cigarette tobacco. Infrared analyses reveal that nicotine is the fatty substance extracted from cigarette tobacco. The results were confirmed by microscopic analysis of the extracted nicotine after adding mercuric chloride, which showed the formation of pink nicotine crystals associated with the mercuric chloride complex. Furthermore, the effects of temperature, extraction time, and extraction agent ratio on nicotine production were investigated. The maximum nicotine extraction rate was found at 60 min. Using a deep solvent mixture composition ratio of 70% to 30%, the maximum nicotine synthesis rate at 70 °C was 8.14%. The purity of the crude extract was 65% at that time, but increased to 98% upon processing.

Keywords: Nicotine, Cigarettes, Tobacco, Eutectic Deep

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1. INTRODUCTION

The principal alkaloid present in tobacco is nicotine, which is an organic chemical. (An alkaloid is a type of organic nitrogenous molecule that has a substantial effect on human physiology.) Nicotine is found throughout the tobacco plant, although it is notably concentrated in its leaves. By weight, the chemical accounts for around 5% of the plant. *Nicotiana tabacum* L., the tobacco plant, is native to America and named for Jean Nicot, the French ambassador to Portugal who brought tobacco seeds to Portugal. *Nicotiana* belongs to the genus *Nicotiana*. This plant, grown in Thailand's north and northeast, is largely used as a raw material in the production of cigarettes by the Thai Tobacco Authority. Unlike most other crops, tobacco leaves are economically valued. Tobacco leaves are traditionally classified into four categories, beginning at the plant's base: leaf, leaf, and tip [1]. Compared to the intermediate position (incisor) and upper stem (leaf and tip), the lower four or five leaves, known as the tufts, contain the least amount of nicotine, the highest concentration of reducing sugar, and the least amount of flavor and aroma [1]. Burley tobacco, a popular commercial tobacco type in Thailand, is offered by grade, which is directly tied to the position of the leaves on the stem. As a result, the chemical composition of the leaves relative to their position on the stem should provide critical information about their suitability for a particular application. Nicotine Tobacco leaves contain nicotine. Nicotine dissolves in a wide range of solvents, including alcohol, chloroform, ether, petroleum ether, kerosene and water. As a result, the solvent extraction method can be utilized to separate nicotine from tobacco leaves using a variety of solvents [2]. Nicotine is commonly utilized as a basic cigarette component in the tobacco industry, as well as the chemical, pharmaceutical, and precision agricultural industries. Nicotine is a medication used to alleviate withdrawal symptoms and help smokers quit [3]. The rapid degradation of nicotine from primary metabolism is a limitation of oral nicotine replacement therapy [4]. Recently, numerous nicotine dosage forms have been developed, including transdermal patches, oral sprays, lozenges, gum, oral films, and so on. There are advantages and disadvantages to each of these dosage forms. Unlike cigarette smoking, the transdermal patch has a steady and sustained release. The most common side effect is a local skin reaction at the contact site, which requires daily patch site changes [5]. Because the human oral mucosa is composed of non-keratinized cells, all oral regions are more permeable than the skin, even though both the skin and the oral mucosa are permeable [6]. Oral sprays can help people absorb nicotine more effectively. Because nicotine does not stay in the bloodstream for very long, this dose form needs to be taken often. The directions for using nicotine gum are pretty complicated: patients must chew the gum slowly until they taste the nicotine, then stop chewing and hold it between their gum and cheek for about a minute. They must then resume chewing and repeat the process for about half an hour [7]. The onset and blood levels of nicotine are impacted by this chewing and swallowing action [8]. As a result, nicotine delivered using a fast-dissolving oral delivery system may reduce fluctuations caused by chewing or swallowing behaviors, and may eventually be used as a systematic technique to assist smokers who are attempting to cease feeling withdrawal symptoms. Rapidly dissolving oral administration systems are solid dosage forms that dissolve or disintegrate in the mouth in less than one minute and do not require chewing or drinking [9]. Despite the fact that this dose form requires repeated medicine administration, it is portable, which improves patient convenience and medication adherence. The two most essential factors when developing these dosage forms are dissolution in the oral cavity and the packaging's tensile properties. The concept behind fast-dissolving drug delivery systems was to provide patients with a simple way to take their prescribed medications. The delivery technology uses an ultra-thin oral film that is put directly to the patient's tongue or other oral mucosal tissue. Saliva immediately wets the film, which quickly hydrates and adheres to the application site [10]. Following that, it rapidly dissolves, releasing the drug for absorption via the oral mucosa [11].

Thus, the current study will use maceration and acid-base extraction techniques to extract nicotine from the lower, middle, and upper areas of tobacco leaves (Figure 1) and determine the nicotine concentration of the extracts. The extract with the highest nicotine level was chosen to be used in fast-dissolving film compositions. In the lab, the mechanical, physical, and disintegration properties of the fast-dissolving nicotine film were evaluated. When someone inhales cigarette smoke, nicotine condenses molecules that are distributed throughout the lung fluid. This represents 100 square meters of the lungs' 300 million alveoli. Nicotine normally enters the peripheral nervous system after leaving the bloodstream and travels to the brain in 8-10 seconds without encountering any impediments (Figure 1). This is faster than an intravenous injection, which trances the smoker and relieves his craving by altering the nicotine levels in his blood. However, various factors are related to nicotine absorption, such as the volume, depth and frequency of inhalation, as well as the body conditions of the smoker [12]. Worldwide, smokers consume approximately 15 tons of nicotine from tobacco per day [13]. This alone is enough reason for us to consider this natural product. This work aims to extract and identify nicotine, the main toxic component in tobacco leaves.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

This method uses an appropriate solvent to selectively dissolve one or more compounds. The extractant is the name given to the mixture of dissolved components. When nicotine is extracted from tobacco powder, its solubility in water is 50 mg/ml at 40°C, 100 mg/ml at 50°C, and 150 mg/ml at 70°C. Nicotine is more soluble in the deep eutectic solvent choline chloride/ethyl alcohol (200 mg/ml) than in water (50 mg/ml), therefore it is extracted from the aqueous extract of tobacco powder. Because nicotine is denser than water and insoluble in water, the solvent-nicotine combination can be separated based on the density differences between the solvent and water mixtures. Draining the solvent combination via a separating funnel allows the solvent mixture to pass through the funnel while polar solvents, such water, stay in the funnel. This removes the leftover water from the solvent mixture. To find the highest nicotine content between the tobacco plant and the tobacco leaf, an inspection was conducted in the first stage of the experiment. The steps were as follows: Ten grams of sodium carbonate, which serves as a base and reacts with the tannins to generate sodium salts of the tannins, was added to twenty grams of tobacco sample, which was then cooked for thirty minutes. The solution must then be filtered using the vacuum filtration method. Nicotine is then extracted in an organic solvent using liquid-liquid extraction with the resulting filtrate. Because nicotine is more soluble in solvent combinations than in other solvents, it is used as a solvent in liquid-liquid extractions. The organic layer is withdrawn from the separating funnel and allowed to evaporate together with the solvent mixture inside. To make pure white nicotine, raw brown nicotine is now transferred for recrystallisation. The solvent mixture acts as a solvent for recrystallization. We determined that the nicotine content of tobacco plants is higher after doing the aforementioned experiment and comparing the nicotine levels gathered. The next experiment involves extracting nicotine with various bases and solvents. Tobacco plants contain more nicotine than cigar tobacco, hence cigar tobacco is used in further extraction operations. First, we will extract nicotine from tobacco using a number of solvents with sodium carbonate as a base. Twenty grams of tobacco are cooked for 30 minutes on a base of sodium carbonate. We call this procedure solid-liquid extraction. The next step is filtering, and vacuum filtration is employed instead of gravity filtration to save time. The resulting filtrate is used for liquid-liquid extraction using a range of solvents such as ethanol, acetone, methane, and solvent combinations. In order to extract the purest nicotine, a separate liquid extraction is performed for each solvent, and the final product found in the organic layer is then stored for evaporation.

Raw white crystalline nicotine, obtained through vacuum filtration and multiple extractions, must be recrystallized. Nicotine can be analyzed using a Perkin-Elmer gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID), GP-100-Printer plotter, and electronic integrator. A bounded phase fused silica capillary column BP1 (30m polydimethylsiloxane) is used. With an inlet pressure of 10 psi and a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min, nitrogen gas can be used as a carrier gas. The temperature is regulated between 60–160 degrees Celsius. The split ratio is utilized for injecting the sample. 5. The retention factor (RF) for each component is calculated using the following formula.

$Rf = \frac{\text{Grams of caffeine (Rf)Distance travelled by the component substance from the baseline}}{\text{Distance travelled by the solvent from the baseline}}$

On a single TLC plate, pure and extracted nicotine were analyzed, and any differences in Rf were compared

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fourier-transform infrared measurement of nicotine in tobacco. The infrared spectrum was recorded constantly. Peak absorbance in the 400-4000 cm⁻¹ range was measured as a function of time. A fully automated approach for detecting nicotine in tobacco using Fourier-transform infrared was proposed. The approach involves directly extracting nicotine using CHCl₃. The samples were weighed within empty extraction cartridges and hydrated with NH₃. The cartridges were fixed in a flow manifold and extracted with 2 ml of CHCl₃ for 2 minutes. 400 µl of the extract was then injected into a microflow cell using a CHCl₃ holder. The area of this peak was interpolated using a calibration line created from standard nicotine solutions treated with chloroform. Throughout the process, the method produced a nicotine detection limit of 0.1 mg/ml, a standard deviation of less than 2%, and a sampling frequency of 6 h/h. When compared to batch FTIR data, which require a 60-minute offline extraction process, natural samples of cut tobacco and cigars performed well. To get a good nicotine recovery for yellow tobacco cigarettes, a 10-minute online extraction time was necessary. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy was used to determine the amount of nicotine in tobacco. *Nicotiana tabacum* L., often known as tobacco, belongs to the *Nicotiana* genus. Cigarettes are the tobacco crop's main product. Tobacco is the principal raw material containing hazardous compounds. Nicotine is a deadly drug. Nicotine substitutes exist in the form of different products. Nicotine derived from tobacco may be a more valuable product, similar to herbicides and pesticides used in agriculture. Certain solvents can dissolve the properties of nicotine. This is the basis for the solvent extraction method of nicotine extraction. Because ether and petroleum ether solvents are selective in dissolving alkaloids, they are useful subsequently in the extraction of nicotine, an alkaloid found in tobacco. If the right petroleum ether to ether ratio is utilized, the extraction technique will produce more nicotine in less time. Nicotine is a deadly drug. Nicotine substitutes exist in the form of different products. Nicotine derived from tobacco may be a more valuable product, similar to herbicides and pesticides used in agriculture. Certain solvents can dissolve the properties of nicotine. This is the basis for the solvent extraction method of nicotine extraction. Because ether and petroleum ether solvents are selective in dissolving alkaloids, they are useful subsequently in the extraction of nicotine, an alkaloid found in tobacco. If the right petroleum ether to ether ratio is utilized, the extraction technique will produce more nicotine in less time. The response surface method is used with a central composite design that consists of two components: ether addition and petroleum ether. The dependent variables are the nicotine yield and the extraction response time. The study's findings revealed that the addition of choline chloride/ethyl alcohol had a significant impact on the extraction response time and yield. The desired outcomes were achieved. The ideal solution is to combine one liter of ethyl alcohol and two liters of choline chloride.

The extraction duration could be anywhere between 10 minutes and 60 minutes. In that situation, the maximum value is 8.14%, with a minimum of 3%. The influence of operational factors such as working time, temperature, and the deep mixture ratio on nicotine extraction from tobacco plants was investigated. The nicotine content of the raw materials, residual materials, and extracts was determined using the HPLC technique. The first deep solvent provided the highest overall extraction yield (8.14%). Tables 2 and 3 reveal that the most efficient method for extracting nicotine from tobacco plants was to use a deep solvent for 60 minutes at 70 degrees Celsius. The results were compared to those produced by conventional extraction with sodium hydroxide and ethanol, which had a nicotine efficiency of 6.5 wt% using the identical raw material particle size. The extract contained a nicotine content. The major areas of this study include nicotine extraction from tobacco and its use as a safe, non-toxic deep solvent method to aid smokers in quitting. It is vital to highlight that its use can be expanded in response to industry needs to include the manufacturing of other goods containing nicotine, a medicinal drug with several medical applications, such as an inhalation spray or a cream for skin application. We successfully extracted nicotine from tobacco using the "liquid-liquid separation" technique. We used a combination of deep eutectic solvents as the extraction solvent. The solvent was subsequently removed from the extract, leaving just white crystals, which were regarded as pure nicotine. Cleansing Rotary evaporation was employed to concentrate the resulting suspension of the crude extract of tobacco roots at 60°C for 30 minutes, followed by an hour at 30°C. A mixed dry sample of nicotine extract and silica gel was then prepared by adding silica gel powder and spinning it until it dried. The paste sample was obtained by leaching with ten times the volume of triethylamine. Third, a 1:10 volume ratio of methanol and dichloromethane was employed to clean it. When the pure nicotine product was finally obtained, its purity was approximately 96%. Figure 3 shows the effect of temperature on the amount of nicotine extracted from tobacco. It was found that the higher the temperature from 30 to 60°C, the greater the amount of nicotine and the lighter the color of the product. This shows that the concentration of the soluble compound decreases faster with increasing time.

Figure (1) FT-IR spectrum of extracted nicotine by normal and eutectic solvents

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